

UDC 622.7: 622.337 (575.16)

**HYDROMETALLURGICAL BENEFICIATION OF OIL SHALE IN
AKTAU DEPOSIT****M.G. Sagdiyeva****I.M. Almatov****F.A. Badalov****I.S. Nurmuxamedov**

State Institution "Institute of Mineral Resources"

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

e-mail: ilkhom90@list.ru

Abstract. Hydrometallurgical methods are aimed at leaching by extracting valuable components into a sulfuric acid solution, as well as selective extraction on ion-exchange resins by sorption and precipitation of valuable components such as vanadium oxide, molybdenum oxide and uranium oxide. The presented methods are not implemented on an industrial scale, since there is no oil shale processing in the Republic. The perspective scheme of oil shale ash processing at the deposit is analyzed. It involves the addition of sodium chloride in the oxidative roasting process, the resulting ash is leached in vats of sulfuric acid 160 g/l, at room temperature, T:W=1:5, duration 60 minutes. The resulting metal-bearing sulfuric acid solution is filtered and sent to sorption, as well as to precipitation. The extraction of metals into the solution is, %: vanadium - 84.3 - 85.6, molybdenum - 95.4 - 88.1 and uranium - 60.3 - 64.9, respectively. To extract metals from the productive solutions of leaching of oil shale ash from the Aktau and Sangruntau deposits, the following ion-exchange resins of the English company PUROLITE were used: for vanadium grade A-109, extraction was 79–81%, for molybdenum, grade A-100, recovery was more than 84–86% and uranium grade A-560 extraction 81 - 79%.

Keywords: oil shale, semi-coke, ash, roasting, leaching. **Introduction.** Oil shale formed at the bottom of the seas approximately 450 million years ago as a result of the simultaneous deposition of organic and inorganic silt [1-4]. In oil shale, the content of the mineral part, as a rule, prevails over the organic part. The composition of the mineral part of shales is extremely diverse: SiO₂, Al₂O₃, CaO, Fe₂O₃, MgO, etc., there are also a number of rare and trace elements: W, Ge, Co, Cu, Mo, Pb, etc. [5].

The content of organic matter in oil shale - kerogen - usually ranges from 10-15 to 40-50%. The elemental composition of the organic part of oil shale is presented in Table. 1. Oil shale is characterized by a very high atomic ratio H:C of 1.2 - 1.8 [6].

Table 1

Elemental composition of the organic part of oil shale

No. p/p	Index	OM shale, %
1	Carbon	75-78
2	Hydrogen	9-10
3	Oxygen	10
4	Sulfur	1,5-1,7

As can be seen from Table. 1 organic part of oil shale mainly contains carbon from 75 to 78%, hydrogen from 9 to 10%, oxygen up to 10% and sulfur from 1.5 to 1.7%.

The composition of the mineral part of oil shale differs depending on the deposit. For example, the ash of the Leningrad shales of the Baltic basin contains about 36% CaO, of which up to 20% is free oxide. The main component of oil shale ash is slag glass SiO₂ [7].

Ash can be used as a raw material in a variety of applications, including the cement industry, due to its cementitious characteristics.

There are huge reserves (47.0 billion tons) of oil shale on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan [8-10]. Only in the Kyzylkum basin there are deposits with predicted reserves of oil shale in the amount of 24.6 billion tons. At the deposits of Baysun, Sangruntau, Aktau, Uchkyr-Kulbeshkak, Urtabulak, the reserves of oil shale are more than 1.0 billion tons. [11,12].

Oil shales of Uzbekistan, in addition to carbon raw materials, contain V, Mo, Au, W, Ag, Re, Cd, Se, Cu, Ni, Pb, S, U, including rare earth metals and platinum group metals.

In this regard, laboratory and technological studies were carried out to extract valuable components from the ash of oil shale from the Aktau deposit (after pyrolysis of oil shale) using heat treatment (pyrolysis), oxidative roasting and the hydrometallurgical method of enrichment.

The object of research was semi-coke after the heat treatment process (pyrolysis) of oil shale from the Aktau deposit.

Results and discussion semi-coke obtained at the stage of pyrolysis, according to the classical scheme, must go through the stage of oxidative roasting, i.e. combustion in the presence of air. At this stage, the residual organics of semi-coke are burnt out and the material is ashed.

For this, a special furnace was created for oxidizing roasting, under conditions of intensive air supply to the combustion chamber. The construction of such a furnace makes it possible to simulate the corresponding process at UTT-3000.

At the plant, studies were carried out on the decomposition of shale semi-coke, for the oxidation of organics and sulfides in the temperature range of 850 ° C with the addition of sodium chloride, which allows a high extraction of valuable components into the metal-bearing solution by leaching.

To determine the chemical composition, ash was used, which is a finely divided uniformly granular powders. Samples weighing 5 g were analyzed on an ICP-MS mass spectrometer. The results are shown in table.2.

Table 2

The content of individual elements (g/t), their clarks of concentrations in the original ore and in the ash of oil shale deposits according to the data mass spectrometric analysis (ICP-MS)

Elements	Clark in the earth's crust	Aktau	
		Ref.	Ash
Na	25 000	7800	12 800
Mg	18 700	17000	14 800
Al	80 500	63000	66 600
K	25 000	13000	15 400
Ca	29 600	66000	47 600
Sc	10,0	12,0	11,6
V	90,0	880,0	915,0
Cr	83,0	95,0	178,0
Mn	1 000	610,0	528,0
Fe	46 500	33000	35 200
Co	18,0	13,0	13,2
Ni	58,0	220,0	131,0
Cu	47,0	77,0	79,8
Zn	83,0	130	149
As	1,7	7,3	0,2
Se	0,05	8,7	9,3
Sr	340	320,0	361,0
Y	20,0	26,0	31,1
Nb	20,0	7,3	7,18
Mo	1,1	360,0	397,0
Cd	0,13	21,0	5,94
Sn	2,5	2,5	0,88
Sb	0,5	7,2	0,8
Te	0,001	0,36	0,18
Ba	650	860,0	831,0
La	29,0	21,0	34,9
Ce	70,0	32,0	56,9
Pr	9,0	3,7	9,4
Nd	37,0	16,0	33,6
Sm	8,0	4,7	4,6

Elements	Clark in the earth's crust	Aktau	
		Ref.	Ash
Eu	1,3	1,6	1,27
Gd	8,0	3,4	6,29
Tb	4,3	0,68	0,784
Dy	5,0	3,6	5,07
Ho	1,7	0,89	1,4
Er	3,3	2,6	2,49
Tm	0,27	0,4	0,341
Yb	0,33	3,1	3,16
Lu	0,8	0,27	0,291
∑REE	208	131,9	203,2
W	1,3	1,5	3,05
Tl	1,0	12,0	33,1
Pb	16,0	14,0	11,0
Th	13,0	8,6	4,5
U	2,5	54,0	52,0

Based on the data in Table 2, in the ash of oil shale - the product of oxidative roasting at a temperature of 8500C, the content of valuable metals of the Aktau deposit increases markedly compared to the original ore, g / t: vanadium from 880 to 915, molybdenum from 360 to 397, etc.

Hydrometallurgical research

In order to extract valuable metals from the ash of oil shale, the deposit was leached.

Leaching was carried out in heat-resistant glasses and flasks with a capacity of 0.5 and 1.0 l under draft. Pulp agitation was carried out by mechanical and pneumatic methods.

The recommended leaching scheme was carried out at different size classes (initial, -0.5, -0.08 mm), as well as under different conditions and acids. The optimal

developed technological scheme for processing oil shale ash is presented under the following conditions.

Fig 1. Diagram of extraction of valuable components into sulfuric acid solution

As can be seen from Fig. 1, the leaching of ash from the oil shale of the Aktau deposit using sodium chloride in the roasting process increases the extraction of valuable metals into the sulfuric acid solution without any effort, including the use of expensive autoclave equipment. The results obtained for the extraction of %: vanadium - 84.3, molybdenum - 95.4 and uranium - 60.3, respectively, at an acid consumption of 160 g / l. However, a further increase in the consumption of sulfuric acid above 160 g/l does not lead to an increase in recovery.

It should be noted that the obtained metal-bearing solutions were studied by the selective separation of valuable metals by the sorption method and more than 70% separation was obtained.

To extract metals from productive solutions of leaching of ash from oil shale deposits of Aktau, the following ion-exchange resins of the English company "PUROLITE" were used: for vanadium of grade A-109, extraction was 79%, for

molybdenum - grade A-100, extraction was more than 84% and uranium of grade A-560 recovery 81%.

Main conclusions

- the chemical composition of the ash from oil shale from the Aktau deposit was determined, samples were analyzed on an ICP-MS mass spectrometric device;

- adding sodium chloride to the oxidative roasting process, which shows the reaction of valuable metals (vanadium, molybdenum, etc.) in oil shale ash and facilitates the leaching process with the extraction of valuable metals into a sulfuric acid solution and selective extraction by ion-exchange sorbents;

- ash from oil shale of the Aktau deposit can be used as a ready-made useful material for the extraction of valuable metals (vanadium, molybdenum, uranium, zinc and REE). Also, the recommended scheme provides for the disposal of residues (cakes) on the road surface and cement production.

List of sources

1. Khachatryan V.G. Experience and prospects for the use of oil shale in the industry of Russia and abroad // *Nauki o zemlyom. Izvestiya Tul GU*. 2016. Issue 3. - S. 216-224.

2. Lapidus A.L., Strizhakova Yu.A., Oil shale as an alternative raw material for chemistry // *Bulletin of the Russian Academy of Sciences*. - 2004. - Volume 74. - No. 9. - S. 823-829.

3. Alzhbor S.Kh., Production of ceramics from waste glass and Jordanian oil shale // *Combustible shale*. - 2016. - T. 33. - No. 1. - S. 260–271.

4. Patrakov Yu.F., Pisarenko M.V. Prospects for the integrated development of solid mineral deposits // *Nauki o Zemlya. News of TulGU*. 2017. Issue 3. - S. 240-247.

5. Antonina Z. Chemical technologies / Textbook for chemical and technological specialties of professional centers. - Yikhvi. - 2012. - S. 376.

6. Rudina M.G., Serebryannikova N.D., Handbook of oil shale processor. - L. - Chemistry. - 1988. S. - 256.

7. Kovalsky V.S., Zubchenko O.M., Boguslav M.V., Oil shale for energy and chemistry of Ukraine // Bulletin of the National Aviation University. - 2006. - No. 2. - S. 139-144.

8. Turesebekov A.Kh., Sharipov Kh.T., Allabergenov R.D., Guro V.P., Ibragimova M.A., Isokov M.U. Non-traditional metal-bearing raw materials: organogenic-sulfide-arsenic black and combustible shales of Uzbekistan // Proceedings of the IX Intern. conf. "Efficient use of resources and environmental protection. environment - key issues for the development of mining and metallurgical industry. complex" and XII Intern. scientific Conf. "Perspective technologies, equipment and analytical systems for materials science and nanomaterials". May 20-23. Part 3. – Ust-Kamenogorsk. - 2015. - S. 273-278.

9. Allabergenov R.D., Sabirov Kh.S., Khushbakov F.E., Analytical aspects of the study of the substance of metal-bearing oil shale in Uzbekistan // Integration of science and practice as a mechanism for the effective development of geol. industries of the Republic of Uzbekistan. / Materials of the Intern. sci.-tech. conf. Aug 19 2016 / Ed. I.B. Turamuratov; State Committee for Geology of the Republic of Uzbekistan, State Enterprise "IMR". - T. - 2016. - S. 124-129.

10. Allabergenov R.D., Sabirov Kh.S., Khushbakov F.E., Non-traditional approaches in the processing of oil shale in Uzbekistan // Integration of science and practice as a mechanism for effective development of geol. industries of the Republic of Uzbekistan. / Materials of the Intern. scientific-technical conf. Aug 19 2016 / Ed. I.B. Turamuratov; State Committee for Geology of the Republic of Uzbekistan, State Enterprise "IMR". - T. - 2016. - S. 129-132.

11. Alimov R.S., Borminsky S.I. (2010) The use of shale tar as a flotation reagent in the flotation of sulfide ores, Republican conference of young scientists "Innovative

ideas of young scientists, geologists and specialists in the development of the mineral resource base of the Republic of Uzbekistan". 70-71 p.

12. Isokov M.U., Yusupkhodzhaev A.M., Alimov R.S., Somova U.A. (2015) Prospects for the industrial development of oil shale in the Republic of Uzbekistan, Materials of the scientific-practical conference "Design and scientific support for the introduction of innovative technologies in the production and processing of oil and gas". 180-186 p.